

IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN THE PANCREAS OF RATS POISONING WITH CHRONIC PESTICIDES IN EXPERIMENTAL DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Rats fed with pesticides in diabetes mellitus were used to assess and characterize morphological substrates and specific features of changes in the pancreas.

Ki67 is a marker of proliferative activity, expressed primarily in the perinuclear region of all labile and stable cells. This is important for assessing the mitotic index in labile and stable cells of each organ.

Relevance of the problem. Currently, diabetes mellitus is the third most common disease in the world and is a global medical and social problem in the healthcare system of patients of all ages and in all countries of the world.

According to WHO, by 2030, 18-20% of the world's population will suffer from this disease, 80-90% of whom will have type 2 diabetes. The prevalence of diabetes in industrialized countries is 5-6%, and the incidence and progression of the disease are particularly high among people over 40 years of age. WHO predicts that by 2025, the number of patients with diabetes in developed countries will increase by 41%. Patients with diabetes mellitus are at risk of a decrease in quality of life, disability and death, and complications of all internal organ systems. Despite extensive experience in the treatment of diabetes mellitus, the majority of patients remain disabled. Therefore, they represent a serious medical and social problem.

Discussion and results. Rats fed with pesticides in diabetes were used to assess and characterize morphological substrates and specific features of changes in the pancreas in specific cells.

Ki67 is a marker of proliferative activity, expressed primarily in the perinuclear region of all labile and stable cells. This is important for assessing the mitotic index in labile and stable cells of each organ.

Specifically, in our study, it was found that rats fed energy drinks and alcohol at the same time had a high positive expression of the Ki 67 marker in the pancreatic epithelium, indicating a high proliferative index of cells, during the first 3 months. This is explained by the predominance of the regeneration process in the damaged gland epithelium and the presence of active mitotic foci mainly in mesenchymal cells.

If a moderate level of expression is detected **at 3 months , then low-level positive expression in the acinar glands from 6 months onwards** indicates that the area occupied by the connective tissue in the pancreas has increased due to moderate positive expression of fibroblasts, histiocytes, and endothelial cells in the mesenchymal cells.

This means that the process continues chronically. In the study, a total of 33.5% of the rats studied had a moderate expression of the Ki67 marker, 65.2% had a low level and 1.3% had a negative reaction. It should be noted that all the cells expressing this Ki 67 marker were non-epithelial, corresponding to 58.61% of the cells in the field of view of mesenchymal cells, and if the Ki 67 marker is applied to the total pancreatic epithelial cells, the average indicator is $23.41 \pm 1.16\%$. (See figures).

Thus, in immunohistochemical studies of the pancreas of 3-month-old rats exposed to pesticides in diabetes, it was found that the proliferative index of the Ki 67 marker was $23.41 \pm 1.16\%$ in pancreatic acinar epithelial cells, and $18.46 \pm 1.01\%$ in mesenchymal cells, histiocytes, fibroblasts, macrophages, and endothelial cells.

Low-level positive expression levels were detected over a 6-month period, indicating that the chronically ongoing negative impact of the process is causing damage and disrupting metabolism in all glandular cells.

In the study, 16.5% of rats exposed to pesticides for 6 months had moderate expression of the Ki67 marker, 82.6% had low expression, and 0.9% had negative expression. This means that all cells expressing the Ki67 marker were non-epithelial, corresponding to a total of 66.21% of mesenchymal cells in the field of view, and the average Ki 67 marker expression in total pancreatic epithelial cells was $10.22 \pm 0.16\%$. (See figures).

Thus, in immunohistochemical studies of the pancreas of 6-month-old rats exposed to pesticides in diabetes, it was found that the proliferative index of the Ki 67 marker in pancreatic acinar epithelial cells was $10.22 \pm 0.16\%$, while the proliferation in mesenchymal cells, histiocytes, fibroblasts, macrophages, and endothelial cells, was $11.02 \pm 0.01\%$.

At the 9th month, a low level of positive expression of the Ki 67 marker was detected, indicating that the process is ongoing in a chronic manner, indicating that the process is affecting all gland cells, leading to ongoing damage and chronic disruption of metabolism.

In the study, 8.91% of 9-month-old rats with diabetes mellitus exposed to pesticides had a moderate expression of the Ki67 marker, 90.2% had a low level, and 0.89% had a negative reaction. In this study, it was found that the expression of the Ki67 marker in the pancreas of the rats studied in this study was mainly carried out by mesenchymal cells, and the cells in the field of view without epithelium accounted for 88.16% of mesenchymal cells, and the average indicator of Ki 67 marker expression in the total pancreatic epithelial cells was $8.11 \pm 0.01\%$. (See figures).

Thus, in the pancreas of rats with diabetes mellitus exposed to pesticides for a period of 9 months, the proliferative index of the Ki 67 marker in pancreatic acinar epithelial cells was $8.1 \pm 0.01\%$, while the proliferation in mesenchymal cells: histiocytes, fibroblasts, macrophages, and endothelial cells was $10.01 \pm 0.01\%$.

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